

ANImal HUsbandry Biosecurity Living Lab (ANIHUB LL)

Overview Report

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Introduction

The ANImal HUsbandry Biosecurity (ANIHUB) living lab (LL) was established at the start of the research project. Living Labs offer a space where collaborative ideas can be explored and practical solutions can be co-created and developed to produce real life solutions by individuals that come from a diverse range of backgrounds to give a whole industry vision. Here, the wider LL group consisted of over 30 members with a wide geographical spread from Shetland to London, Lewis and Harris to Aberdeenshire. The background of the members ranged from Livestock keepers, industry representatives, policy makers and academics. This wider LL group could only meet online due to the wide geographical spread, whilst more intensive in-person workshops were held with the core members of the LL based on Lewis and Harris, Orkney and Shetland. The attendees were challenged to discuss biosecurity, particularly with respect to infectious disease control, in all its facets and exploring concepts whilst offering whole industry reflection. The workshops allowed specific aspects of disease control to be explored by the core members. The core LL activities were captured in Figure 1 to show the level of interaction and collaboration. Individual reports have been compiled and disseminated during the project lifetime and are recorded in Table 1.

Figure 1 The living lab journey

Table 1 Titles and Digital Object Identifier for the reports from the various stakeholder events

Title	DOI/website
Policy brief on barriers to best fit biosecurity practices for sheep keepers in remote areas. Hardy C, Bartley D. (2023).	10.5281/zenodo.7868212
Reflections on disease control measures for sheep keepers, following interventions on the islands of Lewis and Harris. Hardy, C., Bartley D., Burgess S., Mahon N., Melville L. (2024).	10.5281/zenodo.11284397
Biosecurity, sustainable livestock parasite control and messaging. SEFARI case study. Hardy C., Mahon, N., Melville L., Kyle C, Burgess S, Hardy C, Lamont K, Bartley D, (2024).	https://sefari.scot/research/biosecurity-sustainable-livestock-parasite-control-and-messaging
Understanding the perception of biosecurity measures surrounding sheep scab disease and round worm control on the island of Lewis and Harris. Kyle C, Burgess S, Hardy C, Lamont K, Bartley D, Melville L. (2023).	10.5281/zenodo.7867862.
Virtual campaign and messaging for disease control. Hardy, C., Mahon N., Melville L., Bartley D. (2024).	10.5281/zenodo.1128495
Pan-island network for animal disease control-workshop report. Hardy, C., Mahon N., Burgess, S., Bartley D. (2025).	10.5281/zenodo.17406613
Lewis and Harris training workshops for roundworm monitoring and diagnostics	10.5281/zenodo.7646241.

Activity details

Cutting across many of the activities has been the development of a Biosecurity Decision Support Tool (BDST). This report concentrates on the insights and findings from the campaign that have not already been captured, including the online ANIHUB meetings and workshops held in Lewis and Harris and Orkney where the BDST was discussed. Three ANIHUB LL meetings were held between December 2022 and October 2023. The workshops on Lewis and Harris and Orkney were held in 2022, 2023, 2024 and 2025 collecting data on biosecurity measures employed by farmers and crofters with input from industry stakeholders situated in the island contexts. Participants discussed and debated a range of topics, including disease-specific risks, farmer engagement, infrastructure needs, and the role of advisory services. Discussions were structured around definitions and perceptions of biosecurity, practical barriers and enablers within different farming systems, disease-specific risks, engagement strategies, decision support tools, and policy integration in real-world farming contexts, with emphasis on roundworm and sheep scab control as case studies. The goal was to provide actionable guidance for policy makers to support effective, inclusive, and scalable biosecurity strategies.

1. Biosecurity: A Multifaceted Concept

The ANIHUB LL participants felt that the term **'biosecurity' is interpreted differently across the livestock sector**. There may be a need to adopt an alternative term that groups such as small holders and crofters are more familiar with and/or have a better understanding of. Possible proposed alternative terms were disease avoidance, risk management, biocontainment, flock protection or biodefence. However, there was a suggestion that it's not the term "biosecurity" that is the problem, but how the concept is made relevant to farmers. One barrier identified was the **complexity of biosecurity advice**, and that one set of biosecurity practices may not be suitable or relevant to all diseases. What might work may depend on what diseases you are targeting and what issues the farmer is interested in. In other words, there is no 'one size fits all'. Participants suggested that picking one or two disease topics and developing clear and adaptable recommendations about how to manage the specific associated risks, may aid uptake and engagement with the topic of biosecurity. Living lab members also reflected that one set of biosecurity practices may not be suitable or relevant to all diseases.

There were further discussions on this topic that focused on two dimensions of biosecurity – 1) risk assessment and 2) risk management. The members of the ANIHUB LL thought that the key point was to **pick the 'right' disease**, that is something farmers are keen to engage with, a disease that causes problems and might be difficult to manage i.e. a disease that all farmers are likely to experience.

Pedigree breeders (livestock breeders that specialise in breeding animals that conform to breed type, registered with a specific breed society, command high prices and where individuals are highly valued) and commercial producers (that breed animals for specific markets particularly the meat trade where quantity is important and the herd or flock are managed as a group, less individual animal management is possible) perceive risks and responsibilities differently. The economies of scale are generally different for the two groups. There is a need for clear, disease-specific messaging and practical advice tailored to farm types and operational scales, taking into consideration the differences between these two livestock keepers.

2. Tiered Biosecurity Framework

It has been acknowledged that some recommendations are not practical for all types of farmers/enterprises to implement, often due to restrictions in labour and facilities/space. The inability to achieve "best practice" was previously identified as a barrier to implementing biosecurity practices, despite the potential benefit which could be reaped from implementation of partial measures. The ANIHUB attempted to address this issue by exploring what different levels of biosecurity could look like.

Members of the ANIHUB LL were invited to consider "basic", "good" and "best fit" biosecurity (see Table 2 for definitions) and determine which tasks/practices could fit into each category. This information was captured using an online whiteboard. The rationale for this activity was that a more structured approach to biosecurity could better guide farmers in the adoption of biosecurity practices:

Table 2 Definitions of biosecurity practice

Level of practice	Definition
Basic	Minimum standards aligned with Tier 1 of the Agriculture Bill. Includes secure fencing, basic record keeping, and disease status awareness
Good	Builds on basic actions with enhanced diagnostics, quarantine facilities, and staff training
Best Fit	A flexible, context sensitive approach allowing farmers to select practices that suit their resources and goals

Considerations

- Members of the ANIHUB LL emphasized that **rigid biosecurity levels may limit farmers’ uptake** of the scheme. Some members suggested that a cost-benefit approach or points-based system may be more effective and inclusive.
- The members of the ANIHUB LL agreed that all suggested actions need to be presented as simple and deliverable tasks which are practical to implement on farm.
- Farmers need to know why they are being advised to change their practices and how this links to what they want to achieve.
- In addition, others working on farms, e.g., farm workers, stockmen, shepherds, family members, etc., need to be informed of the process, not just the main ‘farmer’ or decision maker on the farm. This requires thinking about how, and to whom, biosecurity messages are targeted. There was a suggestion from the ANIHUB LL that simple and visual approaches could work, e.g., infographics, as these can be seen on a variety of tools, e.g., PCs, laptops, tablets, phones.
- Clear information on the potential benefit of more difficult to achieve practices i.e. those which are difficult for many farmers to implement due to physical constraints (time, cost, labour availability, technological “know-how”, treatment/diagnostics availability) or the lack of perceived need, is required so that farmers can assess the effort vs benefit calculation. The question is, do livestock keepers have access to and understand the advice, guidance and messaging around biosecurity measure implementation and particularly information targeted to specific disease control, e.g. dipping for sheep scab, worming for roundworm is industry interested enough in specific diseases to put extra measures into place? Information developed within the project can be found in Table 1.
- A points-based system could be developed to help farmers select which practices to implement from the suite of options. This would allow for benchmarking against biosecurity levels e.g. Herd Safe (developed by the Welsh industry group Lechyd Da).
- All terms need to be well defined within a glossary for farmers to consult.

Practices suggested by the group

Tables 3a-c and 4a-c list biosecurity practices aimed at protecting a farm from introducing anthelmintic resistant roundworms or sheep scab respectively.

Table 3a Potential basic biosecurity control practices for sheep roundworms grouped according to physical properties, education and training and knowledge

BASIC
Physical properties
Enough fields to allow some rotational grazing/resting
Separate field/pen for introduced sheep
Secure fencing around fields
Handling facilities
Education and Training
Correct storage of anthelmintics, reading product instructions
Basic record keeping – good animal ID, treatment records, grazing and field use
Calibration of drench guns and technique – training?
Access to a lab or means to do a faecal egg count (FEC)
Worming treatment of incoming/new stock
Knowing the farm
Basic level of knowledge of herds-people/staff
Basic flock health plan

Table 3b Potential good biosecurity control practices for sheep roundworms grouped according to physical properties, education and training and knowledge

GOOD
Physical properties
Have a double set of worming/drenching equipment for quarantine drenching
Weighing facilities
Separate double fenced pen/yard for introduced sheep
Enough fields to allow for good rotational grazing/resting intervals
Education and Training
Access to veterinary advice ¹
Well trained/informed staff
Know about Sustainable Control Of Parasites of Sheep (SCOPS) principles and have access to advice
Knowing the farm
Accurate and up to date worming/treatment records
Regular FECs/Faecal egg count reduction tests (FECRT; treatment efficacy testing)

¹Stakeholders placed this in “Good” practice, but it seems to belong best in “Basic” practice.

Table 3c Potential best fit biosecurity control practices for sheep roundworms grouped according to physical properties, education and training and knowledge

BEST FIT
Physical properties
Separate quarantine holding pen/yard with a concrete floor and double fences or solid fenced walls
Loading/off load facility separate to where other sheep can walk
Drainage ditches on the edge of fields to stop run-off water from higher neighbouring fields
Separate handling facilities for bought in sheep
Enough grazing to allow appropriate sheep free periods and short rotational periods
Education and Training
Access to or means to do a FECRT
Well trained and knowledgeable staff
Access to a sheep specialist and/or veterinary advice
Knowing the farm
Comprehensive flock health plan with specific biosecurity measures listed – new tups, animals to
and from shows, new stock, etc.
Detailed electronic record keeping
Other
Keep a closed herd ²

² At this level farmers should be starting to think about the risks from introducing animals to the farm, and possibly starting to breed their own replacements?

Progression from ‘Basic’ to ‘Good’ practice are visible in relation to roundworm management. Examples of this include –

- At the “basic” level, farmers will have knowledge about faecal egg counts (FECs), whereas “good” practice requires the farmer to implement regular FECs.
- “Basic” practice is having animal handling facilities, “good” practice is having both handling and weighing facilities.
- “Basic” practice is having a basic flock health plan, “good” practice is keeping detailed electronic records and accurate treatment records.

Table 4a Potential basic, good and best biosecurity control practices for sheep scab

BASIC
Physical properties
Regularly assess farm boundaries, secure and repair any gaps
Separate field/pen for introduced sheep
Quarantine returning/new stock, assess for clinical signs of sheep scab
Clean and disinfect animal trailers after use
Access to a suitable handling facility
Secure fencing around fields
Education and Training
Access to veterinary advice
Correct storage of drugs, read and understand the product instructions
Basic record keeping, good animal ID, treatment records, grazing and field use
Participation in any area scab clearance programmes
Knowing the farm
Basic flock health plan
Basic level of knowledge of herds-people/staff
Common grazing agreements to include details of treatment for scab control

Table 4b Potential good biosecurity control practices for sheep scab

GOOD
Physical properties
Double fencing the whole farm or at least the high-risk boundaries
Separate double fenced field/pen for introduced sheep
Facilities or means to disinfect/clean shearing equipment
Scab ELISA testing of incoming stock after quarantining, 12 randomly selected animals per group
Weighing facilities
Education and Training
Well trained and informed staff
Know about SCOPS principles and how to access advice
Knowing the farm
Purchase all sheep from a known source
Accurate and up to date treatment records
Other
Regular visit by your vet
Shearers, scanners, and vets must disinfect before and after visiting the sheep

Table 4c Potential best fit biosecurity control practices for sheep scab

BEST FIT
Physical properties
Annual scab ELISA testing of 12 animals per group to inform need for treatment
Double fence fields
OP dipping all sheep brought in
Own shearing equipment and clothing
Education and Training
In an area control program have a uniform keel mark to identify treated sheep
Access to sheep specialist and/or veterinary advice
Knowing the farm
Detailed electronic record keeping
Keep a closed flock
Comprehensive flock health plan, including biosecurity measures for new tups and all animal movements
Only purchase sheep from certified scab free sources

Again, progressions from “basic” to the more advanced “good” practice were visible in relation to sheep scab management:

- “Basic” practice is having secure fencing around fields, “good” practice is double fencing the whole farm or at least the high-risk boundaries.
- “Basic” practice is the herds-people/staff having a basic level of knowledge, “good” practice is having well trained and informed staff

3. Challenges to Uptake

The following points were all identified during the discussions as challenges to the uptake of key biosecurity measures

The meaning of the term ‘biosecurity’ is generally similar between organisations (see Table 5), but the emphasis and actual recommendations used by different groups cover a wide range of factors. For example, the focus of interest and recommendations may fall into one or more of the following categories; isolation and separation, treatment, hygiene and sanitation or management procedures and traffic control. What is important is that **farmers are supported to choose the most appropriate measures tailored to fit the complex set of circumstances or specific context of the farm**. This could be termed as “best-fit”. There is sometimes a disconnect between the term biosecurity and actual practice.

Table 5 Definitions of the term biosecurity

Definition	Source
A set of management practices that collectively reduce the potential for the introduction or spread of animal disease-causing organisms onto and between farms.	Scottish government
A set of precautions that aim to prevent the introduction and spread of harmful organisms.	UK government (www.gov.uk)
Methods used to stop a disease or infection from spreading from one person, animal, or place to others	Cambridge dictionary
Precautions that aim to prevent the introduction and spread of harmful organisms, including non-native pests, such as insects, and disease-causing organisms	Forest research
Prevention of disease causing agents entering or leaving any place where they can pose a risk to farm animals, other animals, humans.	Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural

- Even within the ANIHUB LL members approached biosecurity from a variety of different angles. For example, one comment from a member of the ANIHUB LL was “[if there is] **too much complexity, sheep farmers will close off**”, suggesting that farmers would prefer to follow advice that is practically possible to put into place. Communication is key in delivering the correct message. The term “biosecurity” is not well understood within the industry, there is a need for a new phrase that stakeholders can relate to e.g. ‘risk reduction?’. A good example was the catch phrase “Catch it, bag it, bin it” which was readily understood when it came to controlling colds and flu. **Clear unified messages with practical advice are important.** There is a need therefore to develop a better way to communicate complex messages in clear and simple terms.
- Farmers need to ‘buy-in’ to the recommendations, and these need to be presented in a positive manner. Negative messaging was thought to reduce the uptake of biosecurity messaging due to a perceived “lack of hope” or the scale of the issue being insurmountable.
- There is confusion over the potential differences between an animal with “quality” genetics and one with a “high health” status. Sheep keepers often buy livestock with good (“quality”) genetics expecting them to also be “disease free”, however these two qualities do not necessarily correlate, an animal may have quality genetics, but also be suffering from disease, conversely an un-diseased animal may not have the “quality” genetics sought by a buyer.
- There are infrastructure gaps within the different arms of the livestock industry (e.g., quarantine pens, diagnostic labs). Tools and facilities are needed to implement biosecurity measures effectively, including pens or sheds for isolation and additional staff time to care for isolated animals, diagnostic tools and treatments, but these all need

investment/funding. For example, a lack of disease specific diagnostics is a challenge to controlling disease outbreaks and informing good biosecurity.

- ANIHUB LL participants felt that there was a perceived burden of biosecurity as a regulatory imposition, rather than a means to protect their business
- Vets were generally regarded as trusted brokers of information on animal health but participants highlighted communication challenges around biosecurity and its implementation, such as complexity of messaging.
- Quarantine is often set as a number of days, that can be rigidly applied in all situations. But what does it relate to? Could a more adaptive approach via different management plans be considered, e.g. repeat diagnostics as required and a follow-up to results of these.

4. Farmer Engagement Strategies

The members of the ANIHUB LL discussed how best to engage with the 'average' farmer in conversations about farm animal biosecurity.

Vet led: It was mentioned that there may be little day-to-day farmer-vet engagement around biosecurity topics. The members of the ANIHUB felt that vets needed to be more proactive in bringing up biosecurity topics during on-farm visits. Flock health clubs were also discussed, but some participants felt that the information was not always conveyed in a useable fashion and often pitched too high for many farmers.

Peer-to-Peer: It was mentioned that farmers learn best from other farmers, therefore on-farm demonstrations could be a powerful way to share best practice and provide farmers with tangible evidence of why these practices result in good positive outcomes. This could be achieved in the first instance via the network of monitor farms. Monitor farms were also thought to be useful because of the social element/benefits of on-farm demonstrations for farmers.

Industry led: A suggestion was made to start disseminating messages by targeting the top sheep breeders, linking genetics to health in the sheep sector. These larger breeders have status within the industry and will be listened to by other farmers. These could piggy-back on producer groups, e.g., the National Sheep Association.

Young farmers: Engaging with young farmer groups was also mentioned as a route to disseminate biosecurity messages. These farmers are often interested in animal health topics and the health status of their animals.

Messaging formats

Multi-media approaches were suggested as useful formats for disseminating biosecurity messages. But if multiple formats are employed (Table 6), they must all have a unified message. Approaches suggested included –

Creating the model of a ‘perfect farm’ as a tool or “thought experiment” for farmers to discuss and talk through together. This could be via a physical tool, e.g., the use of Lego/Playmobil was mentioned as a possible method for farmer engagement.

YouTube and Instagram videos. It was noted that farmers like watching these, and they are easy to access and share. This is an especially powerful tool to share other farmers’ and farm advisors’/paraprofessionals’ stories (e.g., the Hoof GP was noted as a popular creator on YouTube). Podcasts were also seen as powerful tools if engaging and relevant.

Social media, e.g., platforms such as Facebook and twitter. Again, this was noted as a useful way to share farmers’ stories. This could be an effective way to demonstrate biosecurity practices in a bite-sized, easily digestible manner, i.e., one post for one practice. This method was considered especially useful for focusing on specific disease threats and exotic disease incursions.

Table 6 Suggested strategies for improved knowledge dissemination

<i>Suggested strategies:</i>
- Peer learning through monitor farms and demonstrations
- Targeting top breeders and young farmer groups
- Multimedia tools: YouTube, Instagram, physical models
- Event-based messaging during sales and breeding seasons

5. Biosecurity Decision Support Tools (BDSTs)

“Best practice” biosecurity recommendations are not always practical for all farmers and farming enterprises to implement, often due to the availability of on-farm labour and/or infrastructure. The ANIHUB attempted to address this issue by exploring what different levels of biosecurity could look like via the development of a biosecurity decision support tool (BDST). The rationale for this activity was that a more structured approach to biosecurity could better guide farmers of different types in the adoption of these practices. In addition to the workshops an online survey was developed exploring the perceived cost and benefit of various practices associated with biosecurity and sustainable roundworm control and to identify whether the practice was considered to be ‘basic’, ‘good’, or ‘best fit’. This was in-depth, multi-step process

1. Initially, members of the ANIHUB LL were invited to consider, via a series of guided discussions, “basic”, “good” and “best fit” biosecurity (see table 2 for definitions) and determine which tasks/practices could fit into each category. Members of the ANIHUB were asked to focus particularly on ‘roundworms’ and ‘sheep scab’.
2. The BDST was then developed as an online survey, to explore the potential costs and benefits of the practices identified, and which biosecurity ‘level’, i.e., basic, good, best; each practice should be assigned. The online survey was distributed to, 1) Moredun regional stakeholders, and 2) members of the ANIHUB. The results of the survey were illustrated graphically and discussed within the group. The list of practices was organised into thematic areas for ease of comprehension.

3. The BDST was trialed with crofters on Lewis and Harris (n=33) to sense check the language used to name and describe each of the practices. Following this feedback, the BDST was further refined.
4. Future work will involve distributing the BDST with farmers of different types and enterprises for further validation. Key themes and findings during the online meetings

The worksheet in Figure 2 highlights the numbers of responses for each practice and the heatmap identifies areas where there was greatest agreement between the respondents occurred. The darker the colour the greater the agreement. The aim was to look for consensus from as many of the participants on the practices from the different themes that were perceived as low cost and high benefit. A range of practices in each of the four main themes were identified by the majority of participants and centered around cleanliness of trailers/transporters and equipment, correct storage and administration of anthelmintic products and good record keeping

The future plan is to develop a decision-making support tool to help farmers and vets identify areas of potential improvements and provide an idea of cost/benefit. Discussions identified that DSTs should be flexible, visual, and context aware. Tools should avoid presenting farmers with lists of unmet 'basic' practices. Instead, they should offer tailored pathways for continual improvement of biosecurity practices based on farm type, disease risk, and available resources. is undergoing further refinement.

		Feedback from the regional stakeholders (n=8)									Feedback from the ANIHUB (n=10)								
	Name of the practice	COST			BENEFIT			PRACTICE LEVEL			COST			BENEFIT			PRACTICE LEVEL		
		Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High	Basic	Good	Best	Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High	Basic	Good	Best
Physical properties	Separate field or housing for introduced sheep	4	3	0	0	0	8	2	2	4	5	3	2	0	0	10	4	4	2
	Access to, and use of, handling facilities (mobile or permanent structures)	1	3	4	0	1	7	3	2	3	1	7	1	0	3	6	3	5	1
	Enough fields to allow some rotational grazing/resting	1	6	1	0	3	5	1	2	5	0	6	3	0	4	5	0	9	0
	Clean and disinfect boots/protective clothing on arrival/leaving farm	8	0	0	0	2	6	3	2	3	9	0	0	0	4	5	4	1	4
	Power wash/clean vehicles and trailers after animal movements	6	2	0	0	5	3	3	3	2	6	3	0	0	4	5	4	3	2
	Disinfect vehicles and trailers after animal movements	7	1	0	0	5	3	2	3	2	4	3	1	1	2	5	1	1	6
	Secure fencing/boundaries around fields	0	5	3	0	0	8	1	4	3	0	5	4	0	1	8	5	3	1
	Use of weighing equipment (manual or electronic) to calculate dose rates	1	5	2	0	3	5	1	2	5	3	5	1	0	6	3	1	2	6
	Separate double fenced area for introduced sheep	1	3	4	0	1	7	0	3	5	0	6	3	1	2	6	0	2	7
	Clean/disinfect equipment prior to sharing	5	3	0	0	3	5	3	0	5	8	1	0	0	0	9	7	1	1
Education and training	Separate quarantine holding pen/yard with concrete floor and double or solid fenced walls	0	1	7	0	4	4	0	1	7	1	2	6	1	3	6	0	1	8
	Loading facility for dead stock collectors away from main farm	1	2	5	0	5	3	2	2	4	2	6	0	0	6	2	2	4	2
	Off load facility separate to where other sheep can walk	1	5	2	0	4	4	2	2	4	1	4	3	0	6	2	2	1	5
	Enough grazing fields to allow appropriate sheep free periods and short rotational periods	0	5	3	0	3	5	0	2	6	0	3	6	0	2	7	0	3	6
	Undertake routine WEC	2	4	1	0	0	7	2	4	1	2	6	0	0	4	4	0	4	4
	Basic record keeping (manual or electronic)	7	1	0	0	2	6	5	1	2	7	2	0	0	2	7	8	0	1
	Correct storage of anthelmintics and reading of product instructions	8	0	0	0	0	8	5	0	3	8	1	1	0	3	6	6	2	1
	Calibration of drench guns, technique, and training in this	8	0	0	0	1	7	4	2	2	5	4	0	0	2	7	5	2	2
	Well trained/informed staff/CPD	1	6	1	0	0	8	1	5	2	1	5	2	0	0	8	2	4	2
	Knowing about SCOPS principles and how to access advice	6	2	0	0	1	7	3	1	4	7	2	0	0	2	7	2	6	1
Knowing the farm	Access to a specialist and/or veterinary advice	1	5	2	0	1	7	1	3	4	1	5	3	0	0	9	4	2	3
	Have and implement a personalised basic flock health plan	1	7	0	0	1	7	3	3	2	3	6	0	0	4	5	1	5	3
	Use up to date worming/treatment records to inform future treatment usage	8	0	0	0	0	8	3	2	3	8	1	0	0	4	5	3	5	1
	Comprehensive health plan with specific biosecurity measures listed and implemented	0	6	2	0	1	7	1	3	4	1	8	0	0	1	8	2	2	5
	Detailed electronic record keeping	2	6	0	0	3	5	1	1	5	0	8	1	0	5	4	0	3	6
	Recording disease events	6	2	0	0	2	6	2	3	3	7	2	0	0	3	6	6	2	1
	Worming treatment of incoming/new stock	4	3	1	0	1	7	3	1	4	5	4	0	0	2	7	2	5	2
	Quarantine shared and rented animals	1	7	0	0	1	7	4	2	2	3	6	0	1	2	6	2	4	3
	Waste management from isolated stock	1	4	2	0	4	3	1	4	2	5	3	0	0	3	5	2	4	2
	Turn treated animals out onto dirty pasture?	8	0	0	0	2	6	2	3	3	7	1	0	2	1	6	5	3	0
Treatments	Undertake drench efficacy check	1	6	1	0	0	8	3	2	3	4	4	0	0	2	6	3	2	3
	Isolate stock on arrival (>24< 48h)	6	2	0	0	2	6	2	1	5	8	1	0	1	3	4	7	2	0
	Isolate stock on arrival (> 48h)	5	2	1	0	1	7	1	4	3	6	3	0	0	4	5	3	4	2
	Undertake faecal egg count reduction test	1	6	1	0	1	7	2	1	5	3	4	2	0	3	6	1	2	6
	Follow SCOPS guidance for quarantine treatment to incoming stock	5	2	1	0	1	7	3	1	4	4	5	0	0	1	8	2	4	3
	Keep a closed flock	1	5	1	0	1	6	1	1	5	2	4	3	0	0	9	0	2	7
Other	Community level disease control	0	6	0	0	2	4	0	4	2	1	6	2	0	0	9	1	3	5
	Island level disease control	0	4	2	1	0	5	1	1	4	0	5	4	0	1	8	0	3	6

Figure 2: Results of the two online surveys, presented as a 'heat map' based on number of responses for each question. Darker the colouration greater the agreement between respondents. Where complete agreement of all respondents was recorded the cell is a red colour

ANIHUB discussions and trialing of beta BDST

Six workshops were held with crofters in different regions on Lewis and Harris during November 2023. In total 33 crofters attended. During the workshops four posters were presented to the crofters. The posters contained lists of disease management practices from the BDST grouped into specific themes ('Physical properties', 'Education and training', 'Knowing the crofts', 'Treatments'). The participants were then asked to provide feedback on the language used to describe each of the disease management practices and suggest potential, alternative wording. They were also asked to comment on the appropriateness of each disease management practice to crofting on Lewis and Harris. The crofters could add comments and critiques either by writing directly on the posters or using sticky notes to add comments. Due to the informal nature of the workshops, there were some inconsistencies around the way in which participants undertook the task; therefore, results are illustrative rather than representative of the participants, and of the wider crofting community on Harris and Lewis.

The aggregate results showed that most of the participants currently undertake many of the disease management practices listed or were planning to start in the near future. For example, most participants stated that they currently undertook the following measures –

- Secure fencing/boundaries around fields
- Separate field or housing for introduced sheep, quarantine area with secure fencing
- Access to, and use of, handling facilities (mobile or permanent structures)
- Correct storage of anthelmintics and reading of product instructions
- Access to a specialist and/or veterinary advice
- Simple record keeping (manual or electronic)
- Have, and implement, a basic flock health plan designed for your holding
- Anthelmintic treatment of incoming/new stock

Areas of concern for respondents

Some of the language used was considered to be overly technical, not commonly used and/or not well understood. This made it difficult for participants to answer all of the questions. An example of this was the use of the word "anthelmintics", which several crofters were unsure about. As an alternative, crofters suggested using the word "wormer" instead. Likewise, the practice "Correct storage of anthelmintics and reading of product instructions" was better understood in terms of the general upkeep of the medicine cabinet kept on farms. Once this practice had been understood using this alternative term, the participants were able to answer questions about its use.

Knowledge of some of the practices listed, and therefore up-take of these practices, was occasionally low. For example, many of the crofters weren't aware of, or didn't use, the SCOPS website (www.scops.org.uk; or in general, any other BDST). They therefore didn't know what the SCOPS guidelines were. Subsequently, participants could not answer the questions around practices that required knowledge of this information. For example, one crofter left a comment

stating - “[I] wasn’t aware of SCOPS until today” next to the practice ‘treat incoming stock with two different anthelmintic classes (as per SCOPS guidance).’

Other practices were thought by the crofters to be not detailed enough to understand what they meant. For example, numerous crofters asked what ‘turn treated animals out onto dirty pasture’ meant, the timescale this practice should be conducted, and what the advantages of undertaking it were.

The participants also felt that some of the practices suggested were not entirely appropriate in the context of the practice of crofting and would be difficult to apply in these contexts. One participant wrote “most questions are designed for large flocks/commercial” and another stated that “crofts are small, there is a lack of space and a lack of options”. There is therefore a need to consider how these practices – some of which are very important for the enactment of on-farm biosecurity – are presented to end-users to be seen as appropriate in all farming contexts. Examples of the practices that were not considered entirely appropriate for crofting by the participants in the workshops are listed below.

- There was confusion about what a closed flock meant and how it could work in practice, there was an in-depth discussion on the ways to interpret this phrase and its understanding differed in different Townships.
- Crofters also often share equipment and infrastructure which was acknowledged as a risk in terms of disease spread. Again this was also discussed in depth, sharing with a neighbour was acknowledged as a potential risk, but sharing with friends and family was very different, you might offend this group if you suggested that this was considered ‘risky’.
- The poor quality of fences on the island was seen as a barrier to the development of closed flocks.

The potential cost of practices (e.g., ensuring secure fencing around all fields on the croft, and enacting island level disease control via barrier controls at ports) and a lack of awareness or understanding of the benefits of certain practices (e.g., the benefits of turning treated animals out onto dirty pasture) were two important barriers to the current and future uptake of many of the disease control measures discussed with the crofters. In addition, the nature of sheep farming was acknowledged as a limiting factor to the uptake of some of the practices perceived to be more financially costly. In this regard, one participant stated that “the ‘economics’ of sheep make things difficult”.

5. Policy Opportunities

Overall, the meetings highlighted a range of challenges (as outlined above) and opportunities (Table 7) for government and the industry to consider and implement in order to improve the health, welfare and productiveness of the Scottish and UK livestock industry.

Table 7 Potential policy opportunities

Opportunities
Integrate biosecurity into assurance schemes and health plans
Support infrastructure upgrades through targeted grants
Encourage vet led biosecurity conversations
Develop virtual tools with embedded resources to allow for self directed investigation and learnings.
Develop new information resources that use 'friendly' language and make more use of infographics

Following feedback from the two online surveys and from the six crofter workshops, the BDST was further refined as a third iteration of the online survey. Future work will involve distributing the BDST survey with more farmers of different types and enterprises for further validation.